

Assessment of Time Management Skills among Final Year Undergraduate Nursing Students at Public Teaching Institutes in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: A Cross-Sectional Study

*¹Sabahat Yousaf, *²Uzma Rafique, ³Iqra Shafi, ⁴Sobia Bibi, ⁵Kawser Azim,
*⁶Maria Yousaf, ⁷Shamim Akhtar, ⁸Yasmeen Akhtar

¹⁻⁸Govt. College of Nursing at Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar Khyber Pakhtunkhwa,
Pakistan

[*¹sabahatyousaf123456@gmail.com](mailto:sabahatyousaf123456@gmail.com), [*²uzmarafique657@gmail.com](mailto:uzmarafique657@gmail.com)

[*³iqrashafi333@gmail.com](mailto:iqrashafi333@gmail.com), [*⁴sobiakhankhan459@gmail.com](mailto:sobiakhankhan459@gmail.com)

[*⁵azimkawser046@gmail.com](mailto:azimkawser046@gmail.com), [*⁶ktkmariayousaf@gmail.com](mailto:ktkmariayousaf@gmail.com)

[*⁷shamimakhtar11337@gmail.com](mailto:shamimakhtar11337@gmail.com), [*⁸Hammaadrahman@gmail.com](mailto:Hammaadrahman@gmail.com)

DOI:

Keywords:

Time management, nursing students, academic performance, CGPA

Article History

Received on 09 Jan, 2026

Accepted on 31 Jan, 2026

Published on 02 Feb, 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Sabahat Yousaf

sabahatyousaf123456@gmail.com

Uzma Rafique

uzmarafique657@gmail.com

Abstract

Background and aim: Effective Time management is crucial for academic success and professional efficiency among undergraduate nursing students. Effective time management enables students to balance academic, clinical, and personal responsibilities, thus improving overall performance, wellbeing and reducing stress. The aim of this study was to assess the level of time management skills among final year undergraduate nursing students at public teaching institutes in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK). Objective: The objectives of this study was to assess the time management skills of final year undergraduate nursing students at public teaching institutes of nursing in Peshawar, KPK. Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from September to November 2025. A total of 122 participants were selected from a population of 200 final year undergraduate nursing students enrolled in three public teaching institutes of Peshawar (LRH, KTH, and HMC). Data were collected using a standardized and validated adopted Time Management Questionnaire, which included sections on demographic data and components of time management (time planning, time attitude, and time wasters). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive and inferential statistics including independent t test, correlation, and one way ANOVA were applied to check relationships and differences between variables. Results: A total of 122 students participated in the study, comprising both males and females from three public nursing institutes. The results revealed

no significant difference in time management skills among students from LRH, KTH, and HMC, and also no significant difference was found between male and female students. However, a very weak positive correlation was found between the total time management score, total time planning score, and CGPA, though it was not statistically significant. A weak but significant positive correlation was observed between the time attitude component and CGPA, while a negative correlation was found between the time waster component and CGPA, which was also not statistically significant. Conclusion: The findings indicated that there was no significant difference in time management skills among final year undergraduate nursing students across gender or institutions. Overall, time management skills did not show a significant relationship with academic performance, although time management components such as time planning, time attitude and time wasters demonstrated weak correlations with CGPA while time attitude component demonstrated significant relationship with time management. The study suggests that structured time management training and guidance could help enhance academic performance among nursing students.

Chapter 01

1.1 Introduction

Time management is the process in which individuals plan and organize time between several activities, to achieve their goals effectively and increase their productivity ⁽¹⁾. Time management is not considered only to make schedules but it also includes task prioritization, goal setting and strives to maintain balance between personal, social, and professional life ⁽²⁾. It is considered a crucial skill especially for students because of its effects on student's task prioritization, overcoming procrastination and helping them to effectively balance their personal life and educational activities ⁽³⁾.

Time is different from other resources, because it is limited and cannot be increased, therefore for achieving success and for self-management both in personal and academic life, effective time management is one of the crucial aspects ⁽⁴⁾. In students to improve productivity, reducing stress, as well as to improve their overall well-being and academic performance management of time is of significant value ⁽⁵⁾. Time management is particularly important for nursing students because of their demanding field including academic overload, assignments, and practical's as well as clinical rotations and to balance their academic site with their personal life ⁽⁶⁾. As it is a demanding field so it requires strict deadlines for achieving tasks, it can cause poor

academic grades, low confidence level and overall burnout and stress when time is not managed properly ⁽⁷⁾.

Nursing students can stay organized, prevent procrastination, and make efficient use of their time by practicing good time management ⁽⁸⁾. Ineffective time management can cause nursing students to struggle with last-minute preparation, poor learning, and diminished capacity to retain information ⁽⁹⁾. Students with poor time management skills typically struggle to meet deadlines, feel overburdened by their personal and educational tasks, and have higher levels of anxiety and stress. Their self-efficacy and ability for professional activity are also compromised by this circumstance, which has an impact on their academic performance ⁽¹⁰⁾.

In order to improve academic achievements and decrease stress level we have to manage the time more efficiently as evident through different research conducted till this date ⁽¹¹⁾. Moreover, when there is no stress then it leads to the boosting of inspiration ultimately concluding in improved academic achievements ⁽¹²⁾. Further, it also helps us in boosting our confidence and keeping us organized ⁽¹³⁾.

1.2 Background

Time management is key characteristics in managing every professional and personal life, however it has great significance in health-related fields like nursing, where we have to manage both our academic and clinical life. The field of nursing requires focus and strict discipline and these are the attributes in deciding our successful ⁽¹⁴⁾. Today's world is fast paced where we are faced with multi-tasking activities at one time and this can successfully be done if we manage our time more efficiently ⁽¹⁵⁾.

If we manage our more effectively it can help us in managing our different tasks in terms of priority which ultimately helps in increasing our productivity and relieving our stress. ⁽³⁾. We are currently living in high tech era where every day we encounter different engaging materials and these can easily shift our focus from our professional life and these distractions can easily be handled if we manage our time efficiently ⁽¹⁾. Time management has also been acknowledged as deciding factor to academic performance while pursuing higher education. It is universal truth that time once passes cannot be recalled, therefore self-regulation and self-discipline is required ⁽¹⁶⁾. In order to have successful and organized life, we have to set our priorities, organize activities which are basic attributes of time management ⁽¹⁷⁾. In order to gain these attributes of time management we have better opportunity to gain it while studying in educational institution and these attributes then finally helps us in successful career. It is also established through research that in order excel in our academics we have to manage our time effectively and then using it in academic learning and self-improvement ⁽¹⁸⁾. If specifically, we want to have successful life in nursing profession then the importance of time management becomes ten folds as

this profession requires stable mind, clear focus and preparedness to tackle emergency situation ⁽¹⁴⁾. Different researches have shown that successful life nursing profession requires effective time management which leads to low academic stress and low academic stress leads to clinical competencies ⁽¹³⁾.

It is also evident that students who are pursuing nursing profession have better chances to have successful career if they show effective time-management skills. They will be able to perform multi-tasking and well in the given time ^(2, 6). Nursing profession requires sound knowledge, clinical judgment, analytical reasoning and patient care skills and these can be gained by effective time-management by giving enough time to the theoretical learning and clinical practice ⁽¹⁹⁾. Nursing students who have skills to manage their time more efficiently, faces low stress and reflects high motivation for learning as evident from several researches which are conducted to examine the link between academic success and time-management. For instance, studies by Ghiasvand et al. and Alshutwi et al. determined that those students who have bright academic life always have the skill of effective time-management. Similarly, conducting research on students who gets higher GPAs shows that they possess time-management skill, says Kulkarni ⁽¹²⁾.

For instance, time management, focused learning and excellence in academic environment are positively correlated which is shown by the research conducted in Turkey, India, and South Korea ⁽²⁾. Further, professional life of a nurse requires punctuality, organization of tasks and responsibility which can easily be achieved if we manage our time efficiently ⁽²⁰⁾. As we know that it is acclaimed universally that time-management is crucial for successful life, however we still struggle to manage time efficient and this is because of the modern technology words where we can be distracted easily by cell phone, television, internet, different social apps etc ⁽²²⁾. Still, not all studies have found a direct and clear association between time management and academic performance. Some research suggests that other variables like study environment, motivation, and stress management may influence this relationship ⁽²¹⁾. It is essential for the nursing to acquire the techniques, skills, and experience to provide better care to patients both physiologically and psychologically ⁽⁹⁾. Nursing students' poor time management has been linked to higher levels of academic stress, reduced inspiration and poorer academic achievement. Furthermore, successful scheduling has been demonstrated to lessen academic stress by lowering emotions of overwhelm, which improves students' focus and resilience ⁽²³⁾.

According to previous researches age, gender, and year of study have somewhat effects on student's time Management skills. Although these studies results vary, few studies highlighted that female students have more ability than male students to manage their time effectively. Kaya et al. and Al Khatib also studied gender-based differences, they also highlighted that female students are even better

in their time management than males, although other studies highlighted the importance of motivation and self-regulation and their effects on time management as scheduling, prioritization, and academic activities balance. Furthermore, studies highlighted that higher academic year's students have even more better time management skills as compared to lower academic year because of their increased experience both in academic and practical sites. These studies results show different variations highlighting the need for intervention to improve time management skills and behaviors of undergraduate nursing students^(10, 12).

One of the most widely used instruments for evaluating students' time management behaviors is the Time Management Inventory/questionnaire (TMI or TMQ), created by Britton and Tesser (1991). Time planning, time attitudes, and time-wasting behaviors are the three primary components that this instrument evaluates. People who successfully organize and manage their time, exhibit favorable attitudes toward time management, and reduce unproductive activities are likely to have high TMI scores⁽¹⁰⁾. Nursing students typically demonstrate moderate to high levels of time management abilities, according to research conducted using this instrument in a number of countries, including Turkey, Iran, and Indonesia⁽²⁾. But it has also shown that these abilities can differ according to factors including gender, academic workload, exposure to formal training programs, and structured instruction^(6, 12). According to several researchers, academic achievements, emotional and psychological health, and professional readiness of students shaped by their time management abilities. Although several other factors affect individual productivity and abilities, but efficient management of time is stills considered is of significant value affecting their abilities to fulfil their responsibilities according to their demanding field.

Internationally, time management skills are considered is a critical determinant for nursing profession growth and development but still in Pakistan there is limited research conducted especially on nursing students. It is very critical to evaluate and strengthen time management skills among nursing students to make them academically successful and professionally prepared as per growing and demanding nature of nursing field. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate the time management abilities of final-year nursing students in Peshawar's public educational institutions. It might offer a chance to identify obstacles, strengthen learning results, and prepare students for the demands of nursing practice.

1.3 Rational of the Study

There is a limited study that focuses on the time management abilities of final-year undergraduate nursing students in Peshawar, KPK's public educational institutions. Since time management has a direct impact on students' academic success, clinical skills, and general well-being, it is an essential skill. In the local context, this area has

received little attention despite its importance. Thus, by evaluating time management techniques and abilities among final-year nursing students, this study seeks to address the scarcity of literature. Policymakers and administrators in education may find the results useful in formulating focused efforts to enhance and reinforce students' time management skills, which will ultimately improve academic performance and prepare them for the workforce.

1.4 Objective of the study:

The main objective of the study is,

To assess the time management skills of final-year nursing students at public teaching institutes of nursing in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

1.5 Operational Definitions

Time Management Skills: The ability of nursing students to efficiently schedule, prioritize, and allocate their time between personal, clinical, and educational goals.

Under graduate nursing students: Students who are currently studying at public teaching institutes in Peshawar, KPK, for a bachelor's degree in nursing.

Public Teaching Institutes: In Peshawar, KPK, these government-funded educational organizations conduct undergraduate nursing programs and are connected to hospitals for clinical training.

1.6 Summary

The introduction of the thesis underlines the vitality of time management capacities for undergraduate nursing students, specifically in consideration of the growing requirements of both academic and healthcare settings. Time management is required for achieving deadlines, balancing tasks, and lessen academic distress, all of which ultimately end in better performance and general health. The introduction covers several variables that affect students' time management skills, including academic workload, institutional constraints, and personal discipline. This chapter further emphasizes the need to evaluate and improve nursing students' time management abilities in order to better qualify them for professional tasks. This study seeks to judge final-year undergraduate nursing students enrolled in public teaching institutions in Peshawar, KPK, in regard to how well they handle time. The conclusions of this study could contribute to creating policies and interventions designed to improve students' academic achievement and clinical efficacy, as well as give a deeper awareness of how successfully students now manage the time they have.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the detailed analysis about the time management skills of nursing students in previous studies. Effective time management have significant impacts on psychological well-being, academic performance, and professional

competencies. It is of significant importance for nursing students of Peshawar to acquire time management habits because of their demanding field. This chapter's goal is to examine recent research (2021–2025) on the influence of time management on the achievement, motivation, and well-being of nursing students and how these results might be implemented in KPK institutions.

2.2 Review Method

In order to collect, examine, and compile relevant studies on time management in nursing education, a descriptive review approach was applied. Research articles, quasi-experimental studies, and cross-sectional studies that investigate how time management affects nursing students' academic performance, stress, motivation, and habits are all covered in the review.

2.3 Objectives of Literature Review

1. To find out both national and international studies on undergraduate nursing students' time management.
2. To determine how time management affects motivation, stress levels, and academic achievement.
3. To discuss about data-driven solutions for promoting nurse educators' satisfaction levels.

2.4 Search Strategy

To locate suitable research, we employed search phrases including "time management," "nursing students," "academic performance," "stress," "procrastination," and "self-efficacy." Studies that were qualitative along with quantitative were taken into account. Electronic databases like Google Scholar and PubMed were consulted to find the material. Time management and undergraduate nursing education were the main inclusion and exclusion criteria utilized in narrowing down the search. In order to guarantee that the results represent contemporary advancements and are still applicable to the educational and clinical setting of undergraduate nursing students, new studies were incorporated.

2.5 The Importance of Time Management in Nursing Education

Time management have been deeply analyzed in nursing education because of its peak significance in students' overall wellbeing and success. A number of scientific studies carried out internationally explored the association between time management and motivation, stress and burnout, behavioral characteristics as well as academic performance of nursing students.

It's interesting to note that there was not a statistically significant association between academic achievement and time management abilities, which implies other variables, such as academic atmosphere, stress management, and motivation, may have a stronger impact on students' academic results. The University of Kerbala done a review of the connections between nursing students' academic achievement and

time management abilities, and the results showed that whereas most students showed moderate time management abilities, there were notable shortcomings in important areas such as determining priorities, getting ready for daily obligations, and keeping control over their routines ⁽¹²⁾.

Similarly, another study conducted at Suhag University highlighted the effects of educational leadership on relationships between time management abilities and competencies of Egyptian nursing student's using cross sectional study design with a sample size of 532 students. The results of this study revealed strong correlation between educational leadership and time management and competencies of nursing students. It is important to note that impact of relation between time management and competencies on nursing students' abilities is greatly affected by educational leadership which act as a mediator for this relationship. The result of this study highlighted student nurses time management behaviors and professional development can be greatly improved by providing and expanding educational leadership. Furthermore, the author recommends that including leadership practices in nursing education is of great importance because it has long term impact on decision making skills, communication, and collaborative work of nursing students making them able to tackle the clinical area ⁽²⁴⁾.

2.6 Academic Achievement and Time Management

A quasi-experimental study done at Mashhad University of Medical Science applied a pretest and posttest control group design to measure the influence of time management training on academic achievement and resilience in female nursing students. After four weeks of training, thirty participants were separated into experimental and control groups. Standard grades and adaptive indicators were utilized to gather data. Analysis indicated that instruction in time management particularly improved perseverance and learning outcomes. The findings about the study indicate that thorough instruction in time administration enhances the resilience and academic success of nursing students ⁽⁸⁾.

In the same way, positive correlation between health and nursing student's time management abilities and academic success was explored in a study conducted in 2005, highlighting the pivotal role of efficient organization of time on academic success. The results were only surprisingly good, highlighting the need for targeted interventions when association between students' time management abilities and demographic variables including age, gender, living conditions, year of study, and desire for learning was analyzed. For good academic results author recommended us different educational programs for strengthening time management skills among students ⁽²⁵⁾.

An educational approach designed for strengthening time management and eliminating laziness among nursing students was also investigated by researchers.

The study concluded that the academic achievement of students boosted after the program, illustrating that structured support can assist students cultivate better habits ⁽⁷⁾.

2.7 Time Management and Mental Health

Outside of learning, abilities to manage time have been linked to lesser stress levels. Stronger coping mechanisms and decreased levels of stress belong to the traits that define nursing students who effectively handle their time.

In parallel to having better use of their time, nursing students who participate in structured programs targeted to better their time management behavior that is, their attitudes, planning habits, and prioritization abilities further see a visible lowering in anxiety. The results presented apply to the inclusion of time management instruction in nursing curricula as an early attempt to control student anxiety and improve academic achievement. This is most likely due to better self-efficacy, a stronger sense of control, and less academic stress, all of which are key in the demanding setting of nursing school ⁽¹⁵⁾.

Another study tested the consequences of a time-management program on ways to deal with stress, revealing that students who committed to the program showed decreased stress and boosted academic focus ⁽⁵⁾. This is comparable with another study that addressed the purpose that time management disposition served in regulating self-efficacy and creative behavior among Chinese undergraduate nursing students. The findings suggested that students with higher levels of motivation and self-efficacy also had outstanding organization of time. The conclusions of the study demonstrate that enhanced scheduling can indirectly strengthen students' innovation and creative thinking in nursing practice ⁽¹³⁾. These studies illustrate that effective planning of time not only helps learning results but also stimulates the building of emotional resilience, an ability that is particularly vital for nursing students negotiating the demands of both clinical practice and classroom instruction.

2.8 Autonomous Motivation and Time Management

Time management provides an important association with students' motivation and self-discipline. One study compared student engagement in online unscheduled and traditional classrooms to highlight the importance of autonomous drive and time management in supporting learning persistence. Particularly in flexible online learning contexts, students who were more organized and self-motivated were better at managing their schedules ⁽¹⁹⁾.

2.9 Strategies to Improve Time Management Skills

A recent study developed a mobile application, "sort-Out," to address time related stress among university students by enhancing their time management skills a critical need for nursing undergraduates facing academic and clinical pressure. The software

was found to enhance students' time management skills, lower stress levels, and increase academic confidence over four-week field research. Students at different levels of behavior modification were helped by its user-friendly design, which promoted improved work completion and organization. These results highlight the importance of useful, problem-focused solutions for improving nursing students' time management in order to promote their wellbeing and academic achievement⁽²¹⁾.

2.10 Behavioral and Lifestyle Factors

Multiple studies have also looked at how digital usage affects time management. An investigation into the relationship between internet addiction and time management among nursing students was conducted in Turkey in 2022. Students who spent excessive amounts of time online, especially on non-academic activities, were more likely to report having poor time management skills, according to the findings⁽¹⁾. Another study carried out in Egypt reported the same patterns, revealing that excessive internet use disrupts adequate time management and scheduling. The above findings illustrate the desire for campaigns designed to assist students balance their online and classroom obligations⁽⁶⁾.

Another study published in Malaysia that explored the relationship between time management and other academic and personal parameters that include sleep, attendance, self-esteem, and sense of purpose painted a more comprehensive view of how time management fits into students' lives and affects various aspects of wellbeing and achievement. It was proved that students having higher self-esteem, better time management capabilities, and an enhanced sense of purpose attending class more regularly, slept better, and functioned better academically⁽¹⁸⁾.

Another study by Tab Vuma et al. tested to see how time management training benefited the behavior of students during the COVID-19 pandemic-related transformation from in-person to online learning, which were characterized by chaotic schedules and a lack of established daily routines. Students who attended time management training were more successful at dividing their time to beneficial activities like eating and studying while reduced time spent on unimportant activities and video games, in line with the study, which utilized a testing approach.

The study determined that although interruptions occur regularly in online learning circumstances, time management is particularly essential. By promoting students' self-control and capability to manage unstructured time, the training lessened procrastination and stress, which impacted their educational outcomes and the overall student experience. This study addresses the worth of time management coaching as an operational way of assisting students at phases of academic and organizational transformation⁽²³⁾.

2.11 Educational Interventions and Time Management Programs

To explore how time management aids nursing students' self-directed learning, a cross-sectional study had been carried out. There's an obvious relationship between handling time and academic independence, as this research indicated those who were more adept at time allocation were also more probable to take the initiative in their educational pursuits. These outcomes underscore the assumption that students who take pride in their own learning are also better at managing their time ⁽²⁾.

These outcomes are in alignment with literature from broader learning environments, which demonstrates that students who effectively utilize their time normally get higher grades and showed better cognitive engagement whilst executing coursework ⁽¹⁴⁾. Another Bukidnon study followed a more extensive approach, exploring how interaction with others, procrastination, and prioritization impacted time management and eventually learning achievement. In accordance with the study, students who had problem in determining interests and were often interrupted by social activities often showed weaker time management competencies, which had a negative impact on their educational performance. Students who constantly prioritized their studies, on contrast, reported more favorable outcomes and less pressure ⁽³⁾.

2.12 Physical Activity and Its Influence on Time Management Skills

In their examination of a link between college students' time management skills and sporting activities, Cao and Jiang reported a positive correlation between regular physical activity and stronger time management abilities. Higher levels of self-efficacy and sensation-seeking, which both enhance students' ability to plan and complete activities successfully, were found to moderate this impact in their study, which included 714 Chinese university students.

Structured physical activities, such as team-based training, were very successful, but high-intensity formats, such as HIIT, demonstrated less favorable outcomes due to increased cognitive strain. These findings suggest that including structured exercise into students' daily routines can improve their time management skills, which is crucial information for nursing students who have to balance their academic, clinical, and personal responsibilities ⁽²⁰⁾.

2.13 Factors Affecting Time Management Skills

In order to determine the variables influencing time management abilities among nurses employed in diverse healthcare environments, Zyoud carried out a cross-sectional study in the North West Bank of Palestine. Using the Nursing Time Management Scale (NTMS), the study assessed key components such goal-setting, planning, and scheduling among 715 nurses from hospitals and primary healthcare facilities. The results proved typically strong time management skills, with substantial

disparities associated with gender, healthcare institution type, and time management training participation.

Stronger time management abilities have been demonstrated by male nurses, those employed in primary care settings, and those who had completed training. The study illustrates that healthcare organizations ought to look at both institutional and specific variables in order to boost time management. It advocates the implementation of targeted training programs that can improve care quality, relieve stress, and maximize nurses' productivity⁽²²⁾.

2.14 Summary

According to this review of the literature, nursing students' academic performance, mental well-being, and future planning are all significantly impacted by time management. Effective time management improves academic performance, reduces stress, and promotes motivation. Nursing students must undergo structured, multifaceted strategies that tackle self-regulation, planning, prioritization, and behavioral modification.

For undergraduate nursing students in Peshawar, these findings underscore the urgent need for targeted educational programs and institutional support systems to nurture and sustain effective time management skills.

Chapter 3rd

Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This section of the study presents information about the methodology of this research study. This chapter consists of describing the study design, aim and objectives, the population on which study was carried out, sample size, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data collection tool, data collection process, ethical consideration, and data analysis procedure done to find out statistics.

3.2. Material and Methods

3.2.1 Study population

All final year nursing students currently enrolled in public teaching institutes of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, constituted the study population. The total population was 200 students.

3.2.2. Study Design

The descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out from September to November 2025 to assess time management skills among final year nursing students in KTH, LRH and HMC colleges of Peshawar. The descriptive design was chosen to examine the relationship between specified variables. This design allows to collect precise data regarding student's current time management abilities.

3.2.3. Study Duration

The duration for the study was 03 months from September to November 2025 in the Public teaching institutes of nursing, Peshawar, KPK.

3.2.4. Study Setting

The study setting of the sample was the public teaching institutes of nursing in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

3.2.5. Sample Size

A sample size of 122 final year nursing students was aimed. On the basis of numbers of final year nursing students at Govt. College of nursing at LRH, KTH, and HMC students which was total 200 students, the sample size was computed using the Rao Soft sample size calculator, a sample size of 122 was determined, accounting for Prevalence ratio of 72%, confidence interval (CI) of 95%, and margin of error is 5%.

3.2.6. Sampling Technique

Convenient sampling technique was used where students were selected based on the easy availability and willingness to participate.

3.2.7. Inclusion Criteria

For this study the inclusion criteria were the Final year students of Government college of nursing (GCON) at KTH, LRH and HMC of Peshawar and those who gave their informed consent.

3.2.8. Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria were the students that are on their academic leaves, and those unwilling to participate.

3.2.9. Study Variables

3.2.9.1 Independent Variables

- Age
- Gender
- CGPA

3.2.9.2 Dependent Variable

- Time management skill/scores

3.2.10. Data Collection Tools

A structured adopted questionnaire was used to evaluate time management skills among final year undergraduate nursing students. This data collection tool was divided into two sections; the First part collected sociodemographic data including age, gender and CGPA. The second section included a 27-item time management questionnaire that was broken down into three categories: time waster (4 items), time attitude (7 items), and time planning (16 items). A 5-point Likert scale, with 1 representing "never" and 5 representing "always," was used to measure responses.

The questionnaire's time planning part evaluated students' organizational, goal-setting, and task-management skills. Students' own views, perceptions, and values

about time were represented in the time attitude part. Time-wasting behaviors were found in the section on time wasters. Higher score in time planning and attitude indicated better time management, while higher scores in time wasters indicated poor time control.

3.2.11. Ethical Consideration

Ethical Consideration was obtained from principals of the three government colleges (LRH, KTH and HMC) and the ethical principles of confidentiality and anonymity of participants were maintained throughout the research process. Participants provided Informed consent and data was collected from those who willing to participate. Data was stored securely and used exclusively for the purpose of research.

3.2.12. Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was carried out using a structured time management questionnaire and demographic proforma. The questionnaire evaluated various aspects of the time management skills including the time planning, time attitude, and time wasters. Data collection took place in classroom settings during scheduled hours ensuring maximum participation and consistency.

3.2.13. Data Analysis Procedure

Data analysis was carried out through SPSS version 27 for Statistical Analysis. The continuous variable time management, was assessed through time management questionnaire, while the categorical variable was the demographic variable. Descriptive statistics was applied to assess continuous variables, while frequency and percentage were used for categorical data. Analyzed data was presented through graphs and tables. Additional tests were conducted to investigate the relationship between time management skills and selected demographic factors.

Chapter 4th

Result

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents thorough overview of detailed analysis of collected data regarding time management skill among nursing students currently enrolled in final year at public teaching institutes in Peshawar. The analysis includes frequencies and percentages calculation for selected categorical variables. Each continuous and categorical variable's descriptive statistics have been presented using tables and figures. Additionally, this chapter also cover the inferential statistics which include relationship between categorical variables and correlation among quantitative variables.

4.2. Sociodemographic Variables

According to the calculated sample size total number of participants was 122 in which 26(21.31%) were male students, and 96(78.69%) were females. Regarding

institutes final year nursing students of 30(24.59%) were in LRH, 62(50.82%) were in KTH, whereas 30(24.59%) were in HMC as shown in table 1, figure-I & II.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Variables

S. No	Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	26	21.31%
		Female	96	78.69%
2	Institutes	LRH	30	24.59%
		KTH	62	50.82%
		HMC	30	24.59%

Figure: 01 (gender)

Figure: 02 (institutes)

4.3 Continuous Demographic Variables Descriptive Statistics

The participant’s average (mean) age was 22.9344 years, with 1.23139 years of standard deviation. Similarly, the average CGPA was 3.4629 with a standard deviation is 0.35391 as shown in table-2.

Table 1: Continuous Demographic Variables

Variable	Sample Size	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
Age	122	8.00	21.00	29.00	22.9344	1.23139	1.516
CGPA	122	1.50	2.50	4	3.4629	0.35391	0.125

4.4. Descriptive statistics of time management skills using Likert’s scale points (frequencies and percentages):

Regarding the statements of the Likert’s scale questionnaire about time management skills, different outcomes were obtained from the analysis of nursing students’ responses. In the table-3 results show that the majority 54(44.3%) of the students’ responded “sometimes” when asked, “Do you plan your day before you start at” 29(23.6%) responded “never”, and 3(2.5%) “Infrequently”. Regarding the statement “Do you have a set of goals for each week ready at the beginning of the week” 35(28.7%) students’ responded “sometimes”, and 13(10.7%) “Always”. Regarding the statement “Do you spend time each day planning?” 47(38.5%) students responded “sometimes”, and 11(9%) “Always”. Regarding the statement “Do you write a set of

goals for yourself for each day" 33(27%) students responded "never", and 17(13.9%) "Infrequently".

Regarding the statement "Do you make a list of the things you have to do each day" 40(32.8%) students responded "never", and 11(9%) "Always". Regarding the statement "Do you make the schedule of activities you have to do on workdays" 48(39.3%) students' responded "sometimes", and 7(5.7%) "Infrequently". Regarding the statement "Do you make an idea of what you want to accomplish during the next week" 43(35.2%) students' responded "sometimes", and 18(14.8%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Do you set deadlines for yourself for completing work?" 35(28.7%) students' responded "sometimes", and 9(7.4%) "Infrequently". Regarding the statement "Do you try to schedule your best hours for your most demanding work" 46(37.5%) students responded "sometimes", and 8(6.6%) "Infrequently".

Regarding the statement "Do you keep your important dates (e.g., exam dates, research paper due dates, etc.) on a single calendar" 47(38.5%) students' responded "always", and 13(10.7%) "Infrequently". Regarding the statement "Do you have a set of goals for the entire quarter" 43(35.2%) students' responded "sometimes", and 16(13.1%) "Infrequently". Regarding the statement "Do you clip or save articles which may be useful later" 44(36.1%) students' responded "sometimes", and 12(9.8%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Do you regularly review your class notes, even when a test is not imminent" 49(40.2%) students responded "sometimes", and 8(6.6%) "Always". Regarding the statement "Do you keep things with you that you can work on whenever you get spare moments" 55(45.1%) students' responded "sometimes", and 12(9.8%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Do you set and honor priorities" 39(32%) students' responded "always", and 8(6.6%) "Never".

Regarding the statement "Each week do you do things as they naturally occur to you, without an effort to make a plan in advance" 45(36.9%) students' responded "sometimes", and 13(10.7%) "Always". Regarding the statement "Do you make constructive use of your time" 40(32.8%) students' responded "sometimes", and 10(8.2%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Do you believe that there is room for improvement in the way you manage your time" 33(27%) students' responded "sometimes", and 12(9.8%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Do you feel you are in charge of your own time, by and large" 37(30.3%) students responded "always", and 8(6.6%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Are you able to make minor decisions quickly" 48(39.3%) students responded "always", and 4(3.3%) "Never". Regarding the statement "Generally, do you think you can usually accomplish all your goals for a given week" 35(28.7%) students responded "sometimes", and 10(8.2%) "Never".

Regarding the statement "Do you often find yourself doing things which interfere with your school work simply because you hate to say "no" to people" 53(43.4%) students responded "sometimes", and 10(8.2%) "Infrequently". Regarding

the statement "Do you find yourself waiting a lot without anything to do" 49(40.2%) students responded "sometimes", and 9(7.4%) "Always". Regarding the statement "On an average class day, do you spend more time with personal grooming than doing schoolwork" 40(32.8%) students' responded "sometimes", and 14(11.5%) "Always". Regarding the statement "Do you continue unprofitable routines or activities" 41(33.6%) students responded "sometimes", and 11(9%) "Always". Regarding the statement "The night before a major assignment is due, are you usually still working on it" 41(33.6%) students responded "sometimes", and 13(10.7%) "Infrequently". Regarding the statement "Do you find yourself getting up late and rushing to class?" 45(36.9%) students' responded "sometimes", and 11(9%) "Infrequently".

Table 3: Time Management Skill Among Final Year Undergraduate Nursing Students At Public Teaching Institutes Of Peshawar

Q. No	Factor/Item	1 Never	2 Infrequently	3 sometimes	4 frequently	5 Always
1	Time planning: Do you plan your day before you start it?	29 (23.6%)	3 (2.5%)	54 (44.3%)	19 (15.6%)	17 (13.9%)
2	Do you have a set of goals for each week ready at the beginning of the week?	24 (19.7%)	24 (19.7%)	35 (28.7%)	26 (21.3%)	13 (10.7%)
3	Do you spend time each day planning?	24 (19.7%)	15 (12.3%)	47 (38.5%)	25 (20.5%)	11 (9%)
4	Do you write a set of goals for yourself for each day?	33 (27%)	17 (13.9%)	30 (24.6%)	22 (18%)	20 (16.4%)
5	Do you make a list of the things you have to do each day?	40 (32.8%)	28 (23%)	27 (22.1%)	16 (13%)	11 (9%)
6	Do you make the schedule of activities you have	26 (21.3%)	7 (5.7%)	48 (39.3%)	24 (19.7%)	17 (13.9%)

	to do on workdays?					
7	Do you make an idea of what you want to accomplish during the next week?	18 (14.8%)	20 (16.4%)	43 (35.2%)	23 (18.9%)	18 (14.8%)
8	Do you set deadlines for yourself for completing work?	19 (15.6%)	9 (7.4%)	35 (28.7%)	34 (27.9%)	25 (20.5%)
9	Do you try to schedule your best hours for your most demanding work?	15 (12.3%)	8 (6.6%)	46 (37.5%)	22 (18.0%)	31 (25.4%)
10	Do you keep your important dates (e.g., exam dates, research paper due dates, etc.) on a single calendar?	15 (12.3%)	13 (10.7%)	21 (17.2%)	26 (21.3%)	47 (38.5%)
11	Do you have a set of goals for the entire quarter?	21 (17.2%)	16 (13.1%)	43 (35.2%)	23 (18.9%)	19 (15.6%)
12	Do you clip or save articles which may be useful later?	20 (16.4%)	12 (9.8%)	44 (36.1%)	25 (20.5%)	21 (17.2%)
13	Do you regularly review your class notes, even when a test is not imminent?	29 (23.8%)	15 (12.3%)	49 (40.2%)	21 (17.2%)	8 (6.6%)
14	Do you keep things with you that you can work on whenever you	12 (9.8%)	16 (13.1%)	55 (45.1%)	25 (20.5%)	14 (11.5%)

	get spare moments?					
15	Do you set and honor priorities?	8 (6.6%)	16 (13.1%)	27 (22.1%)	32 (26.2%)	39 (32.0%)
16	Each week, do you do things as they naturally occur to you, without an effort to make a plan in advance?	22 (18%)	19 (15.6%)	45 (36.9%)	23 (18.9%)	13 (10.7%)
17	Time Attitudes: Do you make constructive use of your time?	10 (8.2%)	19 (15.6%)	40 (32.8%)	32 (26.2%)	21 (17.2%)
18	Do you believe that there is room for improvement in the way you manage your time?	12 (9.8%)	16 (13.1%)	33 (27.0%)	32 (26.2%)	29 (23.8%)
19	Do you feel you are in charge of your own time, by and large?	8 (6.6%)	12 (9.8%)	36 (29.5%)	29 (23.8%)	37 (30.3%)
20	Are you able to make minor decisions quickly?	4 (3.3%)	5 (4.1%)	37 (30.3%)	28 (23.0%)	48 (39.3%)
21	Generally, do you think you can usually accomplish all your goals for a given week?	10 (8.2%)	15 (12.3%)	35 (28.7%)	28 (23.0%)	34 (27.9%)
22	Do you often find yourself doing things which interfere with your school work simply because	14 (11.5%)	10 (8.2%)	53 (43.4%)	21 (17.2%)	24 (19.7%)

	you hate to say "no" to people?					
23	Do you find yourself waiting a lot without anything to do?	21 (17.1%)	25 (20.5%)	49 (40.2%)	18 (14.8%)	9 (7.4%)
24	Time Wasters: On an average class day, do you spend more time with personal grooming than doing schoolwork?	25 (20.5%)	22 (18%)	40 (32.8%)	21 (17.2%)	14 (11.5%)
25	Do you continue unprofitable routines or activities?	33 (27%)	26 (21.3%)	41 (33.6%)	11 (9%)	11 (9%)
26	The night before a major assignment is due, are you usually still working on it?	14 (11.5%)	13 (10.7%)	41 (33.6%)	28 (23%)	26 (21%)
27	Do you find yourself getting up late and rushing to class?	23 (18.9%)	11 (9%)	45 (36.9%)	18 (14.8%)	25 (20.5%)

4.5. Inferential Statistics

4.5.1. Across Two Categories Mean Difference in the Time Management Scores

Likert's scale points were transformed into a single continuous variable then mean and standard deviation (SD) were calculated as descriptive statistics. To see whether there is a mean difference across the two categories, independent sample T-test was applied on two categories including male and female students. Among nursing students, the mean difference of the time management scores between males and females was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.001$, $CI = -8.02545, 7.12000$). This shows that the time management skills across gender in nursing students studying at public teaching institutes is same as shown in table-4 and 5;

Table 4: Group Statistics

Time management score	Gender	Sample Size (n)	Mean	St. Dev	St. Error
	Male	26	83.8077	20.17725	3.95708
	Female	96	84.2604	16.45936	1.67988

Table 5: Independent sample T-test across the gender for mean differences in time management skills

Time management score	Variances		Leven's test for equality of variances		Test for equality of mean				
	F	Sig	T	Sig(2-tailed)	Mean difference	St. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference		
							Lower	Upper	
Equal variance assumed	2.553	0.113	-.118	.906	-.45272	3.82474	-8.02545	7.12000	
			-0.105	.917	-.45272	4.29890	-9.18421	8.27877	
Equal variance not assumed									

4.5.2. Mean difference in the time planning, time attitude, and time waster's scores across two categories (gender):

Independent t-test was applied to examine the mean differences in time management skills across gender. The analysis was done in a sequence manner like a t-test was applied to assess if there was a significant variation in the overall time management scores between males and females' students. Then a separate t-tests was run to assess and evaluate the gender-based difference in the time planning, time attitude, and time waster component of time management based on the structure of questionnaire. There was no significant difference found across gender and each component of time management as shown in table 6-11.

Table 6: Group Statistics

Total score of Time planning	Gender	Sample Size (n)	Mean	St. Dev	St. error
	Male	26	47.7308	15.68071	3.07524
	Female	96	48.9688	11.82811	1.20720

Table 7: Independent T-test across the gender for mean difference in time planning scores

	Variances	Leven's test for equality of variances			Test for equality of mean					
		F	Sig	T	Sig(2-tailed)	Mean difference	St. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	Lower	Upper
Total score of Time planning	Equal variance assumed	7.352	0.008	-.440	.661	-1.23798	2.81380	-6.80911	4.33314	
	Equal variance not assumed			-.375	.710	-1.23798	3.30370	-7.95870	5.48274	

Table 8: Group Statistics

Total score of Time attitude	Gender	Sample Size (n)	Mean	St. Dev	St. Error
	Male	26	23.5385	5.50804	1.08021
	Female	96	23.7708	4.88495	0.49857

Table 9: Independent sample T-test across the gender for mean difference in time attitude score:

	Variances	Leven's test for equality of variances			Test for equality of mean					
		F	Sig	T	Sig(2-tailed)	Mean difference	St. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	Lower	Upper
Total score of time attitude	Equal variance assumed	1.251	0.266	-.209	0.835	-.23237	1.11009	-2.43028	1.96554	
	Equal variance not assumed			-.195	.846	-.23237	1.18972	-2.64443	2.17968	

Table 10: *Group Statistics*

Total score of waster	Gender	Sample size (n)	Mean	St. Dev	St. error
	Male	26	12.5385	3.78662	.74262
	Female	96	11.5208	3.24760	.33146

Table 11: *Independent Sample t-Test For Mean Difference In Total Score Of Time Waster*

	Variances	Leven's test for equality of variances		Test for equality of mean					
		F	Sig	T	Sig(2-tailed)	Mean difference	St. Error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	Lower
Total score of time waster	Equal variance assumed	.667	.416	1.367	.174	1.01763	.74440	- .45622 2.49148	
	Equal variance not assumed			1.251	.219	1.01763	.81323	- .63235 2.66761	

4.5.3. Application of ANOVA

To check whether there is the difference in mean score on the dependent variable (total time management score) across more than two categories (institutes), one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistical test was applied. This test provides information that whether there is any difference in the mean score across the different categories. While it does not show that which mean is different from which one. The outcome of this test show that there was no significant difference across time management and different categories (institutes). The analysis was performed in a sequence manner like one way ANOVA was applied to assess whether there was a significant difference in the overall time management scores between LRH, KTH, and HMC students. Then a separate one-way ANOVA was run to evaluate the institute-based difference in the time planning, time attitude, and time waster component of time management based on the structure of questionnaire. There were no significant differences across institutes and each component of time management as shown in table 12-15.

Table12: *One Way ANOVA Total Time Score and Institutes*

Institute name	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between grop	30.176	58	.520	1.099	.356
Within group	29.824	63	.473		
Total	60.000	121			

Table13: *One Way Anova Across Time Planning Score And Institutes*

Institute name	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group	25.800	47	.549	1.188	.250
Within group	34.200	74	.462		
Total	60.000	121			

Table 14: *One Way Anova Across Time Attitude Score And Institutes:*

Institute name	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group	8.483	25	.339	.632	.905
Within group	51.517	96	.537		
Total	60.000	121			

Table 15: *One way ANOVA across time waster score and institutes.*

Institute name	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group	9.021	15	.601	1.250	.247
Within group	50.979	106	.481		
Total	60.000	121			

4.5.4. Two Quantitative Variables Correlation

A correlation was run between time management and CGPA to check relationship between these two quantitative variables. The analysis was performed in a sequence manner like correlation was applied to assess whether there was a significant relation between the overall time management scores and CGPA. Then a separate correlation was run to evaluate the relationship between CGPA and time planning, time attitude, and time waster component of time management based on the structure of questionnaire. The results indicated a positive but very weak correlation between the

total time management score and CGPA ($r = 0.061$, $p = 0.508$), which was not statistically significant. Similarly, a positive very weak correlation was found between time planning scores and CGPA ($r = 0.035$, $p = 0.702$), and it was also not statistically significant.

However, a positive weak but statistically significant correlation was observed between time attitude scores and CGPA ($r = 0.220$, $p = 0.015$), indicating that students with a more positive attitude toward time are slightly more likely to have higher academic performance. In contrast, a negative very weak correlation was observed between the time waster scores and CGPA ($r = -0.149$, $p = 0.102$), which was not statistically significant, suggesting that higher tendencies to waste time may be weakly associated with lower academic performance as shown in table 16-19

Table16: Correlation between total score of time management and CGPA

		CGPA	Total score of time management
CGPA	Pearson correlation	1	0.061
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.508
	N	122	122
Total score of time management	Pearson correlation	0.061	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.508	
	N	122	122

Table17: Correlation between total score of time planning and CGPA:

		CGPA	Total score of time planning
CGPA	Pearson correlation	1	0.035
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.702
	N	122	122
Total score of time planning	Pearson correlation	0.035	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.702	
	N	122	122

Table18: Correlation between total score of time attitude and CGPA:

		CGPA	Total score of time attitude
CGPA	Pearson correlation	1	0.220
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.015
	N	122	122
Total score of time attitude	Pearson correlation	0.220	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.015	
	N	122	122

Table19: *Correlation between total score of time waster and CGPA:*

		CGPA	Total score of time waster
CGPA	Pearson correlation	1	-0.149
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.102
	N	122	122
Total score of time waster	Pearson correlation	-0.149	
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.102	
	N	122	122

4.5.5. Results Summary

The study overall findings revealed that time management skills among final year nursing students at public teaching institutes of Peshawar, KPK did not significantly differ by gender or institutes. However, a very weak correlation was observed between time management skills and CGPA.

Chapter 05

Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This section presents a comprehension of the study conclusions in light of the research question, then a consideration of these conclusions in light of some of the body of literature already in existence regarding the phenomenon under study. A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out on 122 nursing students at a public institute in Peshawar. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, and SPSS version 27 was used for analysis. The main results of the research and a comparison with related research are presented in this section. The study's pros and cons have been described along with recommendations for future research in the areas where gaps were discovered.

5.2 The ability of nursing students to manage their time

For nursing students, time management is a fundamental ability that affects their academic performance as well as their future professional competence. Effective time management allows students to handle a variety of tasks, such as clinical rotations, assignments, and exams. To facilitate the development of time management, examining time management abilities among nursing students is essential. The aim of this research is to evaluate the time management behaviors among nursing students to better understand the effect of time management skills on CGPA, and how time management skills vary among three institutes and gender based. By identifying time management skills among students and its correlation with these factors the study seeks to recommend strategies for enhancing time management and their academic performance.

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional carried out on nursing students in Peshawar KPK. The outcomes of this study were from 122 participants who were

enrolled in public teaching institutes. Data collection was done through time management questionnaire containing 27 Likert's scale questions. The time management skills were measured through this questionnaire in nursing students and their relations with the selected demographic factors.

For every continuous and categorical variable, descriptive statistics were computed. Mean difference was calculated and other necessary inferential statistics were also calculated accordingly. The study revealed that most of the demographics had an insignificant association with the time management skills. The findings of the study highlighted that no relationship was found between demographic elements and time management skills. However, a very weak positive correlation was identified between total score of time management and its sub component total score of time planning (based on the structure of questionnaire).

The results of the current study showed that the time management skill across gender was same. There was no significance difference found between males (mean 83.81, St. D 20.18) and female (mean 84.26, St. D 16.46). Similarly, a study from Karbala Iraq conducted on 260 nursing students of both morning and evening shifts found that there was no significant relationship between time management and gender. Our study's results are consistent with those of the Karbala, Iraq study. The facilities offered to student nurses and their learning environment may be the reason of this ⁽¹²⁾.

Another study from Turkey which was conducted on nursing and midwifery students found that female students average subscales score (mean=88.15, St. D=11.66) was higher than that of male students (mean 84.58, St. D= 12.15,) and having a p value < 0.05. Our study's results contradict those of the Turkey study. The facilities and study spaces offered to female students may be the cause of this ⁽¹⁰⁾. Similarly, in this study one way ANOVA was applied to assess whether the total time management scores of GCON LRH, KTH, and HMC students differed significantly. Then a separate one-way ANOVA was run to examine the institute-based variations in the time planning, time attitude, and time waster component of time management based on the structure of questionnaire. After a one-way ANOVA, this study concluded that there was no difference in time management abilities between GCON LRH, KTH, and HMC.

Likewise, in the present study, the correlation between time management skills and CGPA was analysed using Pearson correlation. The results indicated a positive but very weak correlation between the total time management score and CGPA ($r = 0.061$, $p = 0.508$), which was not statistically significant. Similarly, a positive very weak correlation was found between time planning scores and CGPA ($r = .035$, $p = .702$), also not statistically significant.

However, a positive weak but statistically significant correlation was observed between time attitude scores and CGPA ($r = .220$, $p = .015$), indicating that students with a more positive attitude toward time are slightly more likely to have higher academic performance. In contrast, a negative very weak correlation was noted between time waster scores and CGPA ($r = -.149$, $p = .102$), which was not statistically significant, suggesting that higher tendencies to waste time may be weakly associated with lower academic performance. These outcomes suggest that while general time management abilities may not significantly predict academic performance in terms of CGPA, certain aspects, such as time attitude, might be more significant.

A study performed at San Agustin Institute of Technology, Valencia City, Philippines found that time management abilities and academic success as measured by CGPA was not significantly correlated. The results of this study contradict the results of our investigation. The facilities and study environment offered to the students may be the cause of this ⁽³⁾.

Similarly, A study from Karbala Iraq which was conducted on 260 nursing students found no significant relationship across time management practices and academic achievements (Spearman's $\rho = .019$, $p = .756$). This suggests that specific strategies, rather than overall time management skills, might influence academic outcomes in this context ⁽¹²⁾.

5.3 Conclusion

The findings of this research indicate that no significant association was found among overall time management behaviours and categorical variables such as gender and type of public teaching institute (LRH, KTH, HMC) among final year undergraduate nursing students in Peshawar, KPK. This suggests that time management abilities are relatively consistent across gender as well as across different public sector institutions. However, a positive weak correlation was found between CGPA and time management skills, particularly in the time attitude subscale, which showed a statistically significant relationship. This suggests that learners who have a slightly more positive outlook on time tend to do better academically. The results obtained suggest the need for deliberate interventions or skill-building initiatives aiming for strengthening students' attitudes and techniques for time management. While overall ability to handle time may not vary considerably by institutional or demographic factors, individual attitudes and perspectives about time can have a slight yet substantial effect on academic success.

5.4 Strengths

❖ The conclusions of this study are essential for both academic success and professional readiness for the reason final-year nursing students are at an essential stage in their academic and clinical development.

- ❖ By covering different public sector institutions (LRH, KTH, HMC), it offers a beneficial comparative perspective.
- ❖ The adoption of a Likert scale-based standardized tool allowed for the structured gathering of data on time wasters, time attitude, and time planning.

5.5 Weakness

- ❖ Geographic and institutional scope is restricted to public teaching institutes in Peshawar, limiting generalizability to private institutes.
- ❖ Self-reported data may introduce biases due to underreporting or overreporting of time management skills.
- ❖ The use of convenient sampling technique may introduce selection biases, potentially affecting the representativeness of the sample.

5.6 Limitations

- ❖ The study is limited to public teaching institutes in Peshawar; therefore, findings cannot be generalized to private nursing institutes.
- ❖ Self-reported data may also lead to biases, as students could underreport or over report their time management behaviours.
- ❖ The research was confined to assessing time management skills without implementing any interventions to improve or enhance these skills.

5.7 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend the following for future research;

- ❖ This study recommends that further study should be conducted in private institution and other region of KPK.
- ❖ This study recommends a qualitative study to thoroughly explore this phenomenon.
- ❖ Integrate time management training into the nursing curriculum to improve academic performance.
- ❖ Future studies might examine how time management affects clinical performance in addition to CGPA.
- ❖ This study also recommends doing an interventional study to assist nursing students to enhance their time management skills.

5.8 Nursing Implications

Time management is a crucial skill for nursing students, particularly in their final year when they are required to balance clinical practice and academic work. The results of this research indicate how essential it is to develop skills in time-management in order to improve academic achievement and future professional success.

The following are some nursing implications that came from this study:

- ❖ The results of the study suggest that nursing educators and curriculum planners incorporate systematic time management training into the undergraduate

nursing curriculum to help students better organize their academic and clinical responsibilities.

❖ This study further emphasizes the need for institutional support mechanisms like instruction, workshops, and time management tools to assist final-year students in developing effective planning and prioritization skills.

❖ The research results suggest that students' time management skills may be modified by demographic factors such as gender and academic performance (CGPA), which should be taken into careful consideration when designing treatments.

❖ The study claims that improving students' time management skills will not only reduce stress and burnout but also boost their clinical performance, which will enhance patient care and get them ready for the workforce.

References

1. Altiner Yas M, Isci N, Alacam B, Caliskan R, Kulekci E. Relationship between level of internet addiction and time management skills among nursing students. *Perspectives in Psychiatric Care*. 2022 Apr; 58(2):758-66.
2. Sadeghi N, Janatolamkn M, Rezaian S, Rashi M, Khatony A. Exploring self-directed learning readiness and related factors: the role of time management skills in nursing students. *BMC Medical Education*. 2024 Oct 3; 24(1):1088.
3. Calonia JT, Pagente DP, Desierto DJ, Capiro RT, Tembrevilla JA, Guzman CA, Nicor AJ. Time Management and Academic Achievement: Examining the Roles of Prioritization, Procrastination and Socialization. *Online Submission*. 2023; 8(6):766-75.
4. Nayak SG. Impact of procrastination and time-management on academic stress among undergraduate nursing students: A cross sectional study. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*. 2019 Sep 1; 12(3).
5. Chacko JM, Varghese A, Rajesh N. Impact of time management program on stress and coping strategies adopted by nursing students with regard to academic performance. *IP Journal of Paediatrics and Nursing Science*. 2023 May 8;6(1):48-56.
6. Ali HF, Mousa MA, Atta MH, Morsy SR. Exploring the association between internet addiction and time management among undergraduate nursing students. *BMC nursing*. 2024 Sep 11; 23(1):632.
7. Ahlawat P, Sharma P, Tyagi N. Educational Module Effectiveness on Academic Procrastination and Time Management Skills among Nursing Student: Quasi Experimental Study. *J Clin Biomed Sci*. 2025 Mar 25; 15(1):49-54.
8. Ashrafi S. Effectiveness of Time Management Training on Nursing Students' Academic Achievement and Resilience. *Future of medical education journal*. 2021; doi:10.22038/FMEJ.2020.47527.1323

9. Abd El-Aziz TL, Eid NM, Safan SM. Test-anxiety and skills of time-management among faculty nursing students. *Journal of American Science*. 2012; 8(4):261-9.
10. Kaya H, Kaya N, Palloş AÖ, Küçük L. Assessing time-management skills in terms of age, gender, and anxiety levels: A study on nursing and midwifery students in Turkey. *Nurse education in practice*. 2012 Sep 1; 12(5):284-8.
11. Ahmad S, Batool A, Choudhry AH. Path Relationship of Time Management and Academic Achievement of Students in Distance Learning Institutions. *Pakistan Journal of Distance and Online Learning*. 2019; 5(2):191-208.
12. Mansoor HI. The relationship between time management skills and the academic performance of nursing students at university of Karbala, Iraq. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*. 2025 Jan 21; 5(01):35-44.
13. Lin Y, Wang X, Zhang X, Hu H, Liu L, Pang K, Li Y, Hu C, Sun Z, Li X. The impact of undergraduate nursing students' time management disposition on innovative behaviour: The chain mediating role of academic self-efficacy and flow experience. *Frontiers in psychology*. 2025 Feb 19; 16:1447121.
14. Fu Y, Wang Q, Wang X, Zhong H, Chen J, Fei H, Yao Y, Xiao Y, Li W, Li N. Unlocking academic success: the impact of time management on college students' study engagement. *BMC psychology*. 2025 Apr 2; 13(1):323.
15. Zhang F, Liu J, an M, Gu H. The effect of time management training on time management and anxiety among nursing undergraduates. *Psychology, health & medicine*. 2021 Oct 21; 26(9):1073-8.
16. Mercanlıoğlu Ç. The relationship of time management to academic performance of master level students. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*. 2010; 2(1):25-36.
17. Pandian AV. EFFECT OF TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF ETHIOPIA: THE CASE OF DIRE DAWA UNIVERSITY.
18. Masnan F, Abd Rani MJ, Alias NS, Esquivias MA, Shaari MS, Kustiningsih N. The role of sense of purpose, time management, attendance, sleep and self-esteem in academic performance among university students in Malaysia. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*. 2025 Jan 1; 11:101258.
19. Zeng H, Xin Y. Comparing learning persistence and engagement in asynchronous and synchronous online learning, the role of autonomous academic motivation and time management. *Interactive Learning Environments*. 2025 Jan 2; 33(1):276-95.
20. Cao Y, Jiang Y. The effects of physical exercise on the time management of college students: a chain mediation effect test. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2025 Jul 2; 16:1599833.

21. Alhasani M, Orji R. Promoting stress management among students in higher education: Evaluating the effectiveness of a persuasive time management mobile app. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*. 2025 Jan 2; 41(1):219-41.
22. Zyoud RA. Factors influencing time management skills among nurses in North West Bank, Palestine. *BMC nursing*. 2023 Oct 17; 22(1):386.
23. Tabvuma V, Carter-Rogers K, Brophy T, Smith SM, Sutherland S. Transitioning from in person to online learning during a pandemic: an experimental study of the impact of time management training. *Higher Education Research & Development*. 2022 Nov 10; 41(7):2441-57.
24. Amin SM, El-Sayed AA, Othman AA, Ali AS, Elfeshawy NI, El-Sherbini HH, Mahmoud AA, Atta MH. Transforming nursing education: the power of educational leadership in optimizing time management and competency. *BMC nursing*. 2025 Jul 7; 24(1):870.
25. Yousefi S, Hrsej Z, Jannat Alipour Z, Afrrouz M, Navabi N. The relationship between time management skills and academic achievement in nursing and public health students. *Medical Education Journal*. 2017 Sep 15; 5(2):29-40.